

SOME CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE ADOPTION OF THE NEW LAW ON NON-COMMERCIAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The right-wing opposition is promoting a new bill on non-commercial organizations, among the main provisions are the reduction of the registration time of these structures, as well as the (im)possibility of their financing from abroad. Attitudes towards the activities of non-commercial organizations in a number of post-Soviet countries are usually viewed differently. Some call them “grantophages”, others say that civic activists are engaged in one important and necessary thing - human rights activities, while others resort to conspiracy theory, noting that through such NGOs, the government “in the shadows” tries to intervene in the politics of countries with specific goals, especially in states that do not yet have a fully developed democratic system.

In this article we aim to highlight the basic issues regarding the evolution and context of the adoption of the non-commercial law, the opinions regarding this document, as well as the main provisions of the law that have sparked several discussions among civil society representatives, but especially among politicians from our country.

Keywords: law, non-commercial organizations, debates, Parliament, civil society representatives.

UNELE CONSIDERAȚII REFERITOR LA ADOPTAREA NOII LEGI PRIVIND ORGANIZAȚIILE NECOMERCIALE DIN REPUBLICA MOLDOVA

Opoziția de dreapta promovează un nou proiect de lege privind organizațiile necomerciale. Printre principalele prevederi se numără reducerea timpului de înregistrare ale acestor structuri, precum și (im)posibilitatea finanțării externe. Atitudinea față de activitățile organizațiilor necomerciale dintr-o serie de state din spațiul post-sovietic diferă de la o țară la alta. Unii le numesc „grantofagi”, alții spun că activiștii civici sunt angajați într-un lucru important și necesar; de exemplu, activitățile privind apărarea drepturilor omului, în timp ce alții recurg la teoria conspirației, menționând că prin astfel de ONG-uri, guvernul „din umbră” încearcă să intervină în politica țărilor cu scopuri specifice, îndeosebi în statele care nu au încă un sistem democratic pe deplin dezvoltat.

În prezentul articol ne propunem să evidențiem aspectele de bază privind evoluția și contextul adoptării legii cu privire la organizațiile necomerciale, opiniile vizavi de acest document, precum și principalele prevederi ale legii, care au stârnit mai multe discuții atât printre reprezentanții societății civile, dar în special în rândul politicienilor din țara noastră.

Cuvinte-cheie: lege, organizații necomerciale, dezbateri, Parlament, reprezentanți ai societății civile.

QUELQUES CONSIDÉRATIONS CONCERNANT L'ADOPTION DE LA NOUVELLE LOI SUR LES ORGANISATIONS NON COMMERCIALES EN RÉPUBLIQUE DE MOLDOVA

L'opposition de droite promeut un nouveau projet de loi sur les organisations non commerciales. Parmi les principales dispositions figurent la réduction du temps d'enregistrement de ces structures, ainsi que la (im)possibilité d'un financement externe. L'attitude à l'égard des activités des organisations non commerciales, dans un certain nombre d'états de l'espace post-Soviétique diffère d'un pays à l'autre. Certains les appellent des "grantophages", d'autres disent que les militants civiques sont engagés dans une chose importante et nécessaire, par exemple des activités de défense des droits de l'homme, tandis que d'autres recourent à la théorie du complot, notant que par le biais de telles ONG, le gouvernement "fantôme" tente d'intervenir dans la politique des pays ayant des objectifs spécifiques, en special dans les États qui n'ont pas encore un système démocratique pleinement développé.

Dans cet article, nous avons l'intention de souligner les aspects du développement et le contexte de l'adoption de la loi sur les organisations non commerciales, les avis concernant ce document, ainsi que les principales dispositions de la loi, qui a suscité plusieurs discussions entre les représentants de la société civile, en particulier parmi les politiciens de notre pays.

***Mots-clés:** droit, organisations non commerciales, débats, Parlement, représentants de la société civile.*

НЕКОТОРЫЕ СУЖДЕНИЯ ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНО ПРИНЯТИЯ НОВОГО ЗАКОНА О НЕКОММЕРЧЕСКИХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ МОЛДОВА

Правая оппозиция продвигает новый закон о некоммерческих организациях. Основные положения включают сокращение времени регистрации этих структур, а также (не)возможность внешнего финансирования. Отношение к деятельности некоммерческих организаций в ряде постсоветских стран отличается. Одни называют их «грантоедомы», другие считают, что гражданские активисты занимаются важным и нужным делом, например, правозащитной деятельностью, третьи же прибегают к теории заговора, отмечая, что через такие НПО «теневые правительства» стремятся вмешиваться в политику государств, особенно в тех странах, где еще слабо развиты демократические системы.

В данной статье мы стремимся осветить основные аспекты эволюции и контекст принятия закона о некоммерческих организациях, различные мнения относительно этого документа, а также основные положения закона, которые вызвали много дискуссий как среди представителей гражданского общества, так и особенно в политической среде.

***Ключевые слова:** закон, некоммерческие организации, дебаты, парламент, представители гражданского общества.*

Introduction

The right-wing opposition is promoting a new bill on non-commercial organizations, among the main provisions are the reduction of the registration time of these structures, as well as the (im)possibility of their financing from abroad. Attitudes towards the activities of non-commercial organizations in a number of post-Soviet countries are usually viewed differently. Some call them "grantophages", others say that civic activists are engaged in one important

and necessary thing - human rights activities, while others resort to conspiracy theory, noting that through such NGOs, the government "in the shadows" tries to intervene in the politics of countries with specific goals, especially in states that do not yet have a fully developed democratic system.

In this article we aim to highlight the basic issues regarding the evolution and context of the adoption of the non-commercial law, the opinions regarding this document, as well as the main provisions of the law that have sparked several discussions among

civil society representatives, but especially among politicians from our country.

Ideas and discussions

Opinions on the regulation of the non-commercial organizations activity differ from those of civil society representatives and deputies from the Republic of Moldova's Parliament. Next we will make a brief presentation of the evolution regarding the adoption of the NGO law, and also will reveal some opinions expressed by various experts and politicians in this regard in order to create a clearer picture to the reader about the need or ignorance to adopt the new bill.

Thus, the political analyst Serghei Manastîrlî considers that many legal acts regarding the legislative regulation of non-commercial organizations activities are outdated. "The world is moving forward, and the activities of NGOs in the country must meet the requirements of the weather. It is another matter that the state sees a kind of threat in the work of such non-governmental associations, trying to reduce this potential danger", he said. At the same time, the risks of the new bill, so actively promoted by the representatives of the right-wing political forces in Moldova, may be mentioned, such as that the draft contains provisions according to which NGOs and even political parties can be funded from abroad. And this can become a big risk for the country's sovereignty, for the independent adoption of domestic political decisions by the country. However, in the past there has been a tacit fundraising for the activities of Moldovan parties, and this money has often been perceived as a factor of foreign influence on the country's policy. "The problem is not the wording of the law itself, but the fact that so far no one has been punished for gross violation of it", said Manastîrlî. According to the expert, previously in the activities of some, especially the center-right parties, there was a factor of external funding, but the experts of these political forces carried out these tranches so secretly

that the state control authorities could not intervene in no way to stop such illegality and even partially subversive activity.

In the same vein, political analyst Boris Shapovalov considers that such facilities open a room for foreign-funded associations, which we do not know what they do in our country. The expert points out that there is already a law on non-commercial associations, which clearly defines who and how they can be created, what their goals and objectives are. Laws on foundations, non-profit organizations have also been adopted, and each country has its own approach to this. Interestingly, the expert believes that the new bill would be an idea that is imposed on young democrats, so that the West has the opportunity to continue its policy through these organizations. "First of all, non-governmental organizations are created on the territory of the state that are not registered anywhere, their sources of financing are not clear, and then they put pressure on the authorities in the country to please those who sponsor these associations. This is a hidden form of government of entire states through NGOs. At the same time, in a number of countries, including the post-Soviet ones, decisions are made at the level of the central government that limits such practices and this is done not to violate democratic rules, but to limit the factor of external influence on decisions", added Shapovalov. [16]

The first hot statement against this bill was made by Prime Minister Ion Chicu on June 1, 2020. He said that those who want to vote the law on NGOs, in reality intend to liquidate the Republic of Moldova. On the other hand, in the opinion of the president of the Action and Solidarity Party (ASP), Maia Sandu, the law does not contain wording that would be against the interests of the country. "It is completely incomprehensible why the Prime Minister asks such questions about a law that is necessary in a democratic country and it is obvious that the European

Union would never insist on formulations or a law that would go against the interests of the country or against the democratic processes”.

The opinion of the President of the country Igor Dodon is that the NGO Law would be an “interesting, contradictory one and, certainly, in the current wording it does not correspond to the interests of the Republic of Moldova”. According to the head of state, the Socialist Party faction will not vote in Parliament, and if this law passes, the president will not promulgate it. In the same context, Igor Dodon claims that the law was voted in the first reading even during the Filip government (the former prime-minister). “Now everyone, the opposition, the external partners, insist on its approval in the final reading. The law, in the proposed wording, allows NGOs to provide services to political parties and access funding from abroad”, the head of state said. Igor Dodon believes that in this way NGOs can help political parties in their political activity, without the latter reporting their income, which would mean an external involvement in the political life of the Republic of Moldova.

“Our opponents say that if we do not adopt this law, we will not receive EU funding. In such conditions, we do not need funding”, declared the head of state. If the coalition partners of the Socialists vote the law, this will mean that they are in breach of the coalition agreement and if, as a result, the law passes Parliament, the agreement will be denounced. These actions were appealed by the fact that the deputies of the ASP faction, the ACUM Bloc, asked to convene Parliament sitting for May 29, to vote on the bills necessary for disbursement of European macro-financial assistance, including the NGO Law. Then the president of the faction, Igor Grosu, said that there is very little time, of the order of a week, to succeed in fulfilling the conditionalities for granting the second and third tranches of the macro-financial assistance. If the

conditionalities are not met, then Moldova risks losing macro-financial assistance in the amount of 600 million lei [5].

On June 4, 2020 the country’s president, Igor Dodon, mentioned that the law on the activity of NGOs could be passed by the Parliament next week. The head of state said that during a meeting with lawyers from the Government, Parliament and the Presidency, some recommendations were made to Parliament [17]. The problems were related to art. 6 paragraph 4, which refer to the way in which NGOs can help political parties: “The non-commercial organization cannot support materially or cannot provide free services to political parties and socio-political organizations. Non-commercial organizations formed by political parties and socio-political organizations may provide free services to political parties and socio-political organizations in order to strengthen their organizational capacities”, but also by paragraph 5 of the same article: “During the election campaign, the non-commercial organization may not support material or cannot provide free services to electoral contestants or cannot make electoral agitation”. The Socialist Party, but also the president Igor Dodon announced that they will not accept the law in the existing version, and the changes decided at the meeting of the governing coalition have not been specified yet [4].

In the president’s opinion, “In some European countries it is expressly stated that if NGOs are involved in politics, then they must report publicly where their income comes from”. The President gave the example of Hungary and Poland, which are European countries, and said that Moldova must vote on a similar law [17].

It should be noted that the opposition and independent experts say that Dodon worries that he could be left without funding in the election campaign, as the NGO law does not allow donations to political parties. During the debates in the Legal Committee,

the Socialist Party proposed that the law enters into force in 2021, ie after the elections [8].

In particular, the deputy of the Action and Solidarity Party, Sergiu Litvinenco, pointed out that Article 6, paragraph 5 is not to the liking of the Socialists, especially Igor Dodon. “According to this law, no non-commercial organization will be able to get involved in the election campaign and will not be able to make electoral agitation, either open or hidden. Foundations also fall into the category of non-commercial organizations. It is now well known that the president’s wife has a foundation called “From the Heart (Din Suflet)”, which is funded in an absolutely non-transparent way. If this law comes into force, Igor Dodon will no longer be able to be supported in campaigns by the first lady’s foundation. This foundation should suspend its activity during the election campaign and will not be able to continue to support the candidate Igor Dodon by corrupting the voters, by offering gifts, as has been done so far. This is the real cause beyond the pretexts voiced by Dodon and Chicu”, the deputy also underlined.

On June 8, 2020, the meeting of the Democratic Party (DP) faction took place and all colleagues expressed their support for this Law. It would be incorrect for DP not to support this bill. The Democratic Party leader, when he was Prime Minister, promoted this law and negotiated it in Brussels. Moldova cannot afford to not receive money. DP will not compromise on non-voting. “We are firmly convinced to support this law and the coalition colleagues will limit themselves to imposing conditionalities on their part. I understand that there are fears that through the NGOs the political parties will be financed in the electoral campaign but this is just populism”, said the democratic deputy Ion Leucă. Citizens must understand that it is not the EU that needs these conditions, but the Republic of Moldova. All conditionalities are part of the national action plan on the implementation of the Association Agreement. [15] Ion

Leucă mentioned that the second tranche of 30 million euros of the macro-financial assistance, granted by the European Union, is extremely necessary, in the conditions of the pandemic in the country. [3]

On 09.06.2020, President Igor Dodon announced that there was a consensus on the controversial Law on the activity of NGOs to amend some articles that would minimize the risks of involvement of external forces in the domestic policy of the Republic of Moldova. At the same time, if these amendments are supported, then the NGO Law, most likely, this week will be voted in the second reading to be sent for promulgation to the country’s president”, said Igor Dodon after the weekly meeting with the speaker and the prime minister. [14] Earlier, Igor Dodon and Prime Minister Ion Chicu stated that this law seeks to take over the leadership of the Republic of Moldova from abroad, through NGOs, which will be free to receive funding from abroad. We remind that the adoption of the NGO Law is one of the conditionalities of the European Union, for the disbursement of European macro-financial assistance. [2] In order to receive the second tranche of the macro-financial support provided by the EU, Parliament must meet all the conditionalities, and the last condition is the approval of the NGO Law.

The president’s statements on identifying consensus for amending several articles of the NGO law were criticized by ASP deputy Sergiu Litvinenco. He considers that “absolute prohibitions on commenting / promoting public policies are introduced. For example, an environmental NGO cannot criticize a bill that is against the environment. Moreover, such bans do not exist in Russia, Azerbaijan or Belarus”. [1] Sergiu Litvinenco also says that another amendment leaked by the Socialists provides for a ban on the monitoring of elections by NGOs - for example, Promo-LEX will no longer be able to monitor the elections. On the other hand, “the ban on NGOs, including foundations, from

conducting electoral agitation is excluded”. Litvinenco says that this is “a special provision for the “From the Soul (Din Suflet)” Foundation of Galina Dodon (the wife of the country’s president) to make an agitation for Igor Dodon”. The presidential institution did not reply to these allegations. However, Igor Dodon said in his vlog that the accusations of the opposition are unfounded, because “election campaigns cannot be financed from funds other than those stated in party reports”. [9] Mr Litvinenco also added about the impossibility of amending the articles given that the Legal Committee has already approved the final report on that bill.

In the same vein, MP Monica Babuc from the Democratic Party said that other amendments, except those examined in the Legal Committee for appointments and immunities were not discussed by the parliamentary majority. That is, 104 amendments were discussed in the Legal Committee and by consensus they were voted by all committee members. [13]

Also the Democratic Party announced that it will vote only on the amendments to the Law on NGOs discussed and agreed with the European Union Delegation in Chisinau. The honorary president of the Democratic Party, the deputy Dumitru Diacov, also announced the support of only those amendments of the law that will be coordinated with the EU. He specified that he spoke on this subject with the socialist deputy, Vasile Bolea, whom he asked “to coordinate all the amendments with our European partners”. “It would be good for this law, on which the second tranche of EU credit depends, to be voted on by all parliamentary factions. I believe that no one should be stubborn and create problems at the final approval of this law. Whether they are even from the opposition or from the Socialist Party!”, Dumitru Diacov also opined. [10]

Civil society representatives have differing views on the amendments to the NGO Law, and

we will continue to focus on the brief presentation of their main ideas. They consider that the amendments proposed by the Socialist Party deputies to the Law on Non-Commercial Organizations are unacceptable for a democratic society and come to introduce limitations that can only exist in states with dictatorships. Moreover, they will be deprived of the right to rule on public policies, but also to monitor elections and election campaigns.

Thus, the political expert from IDIS “Viitorul”, Veaceslav Berbeca, considers that the proposal related to the ban on election monitoring is an attempt to drastically limit, even to ban the participation of NGOs in monitoring elections. However, the role of NGOs is to highlight certain violations of the law. And this happens under the conditions where in the Republic of Moldova there are still slippages in terms of democracy, and the state institutions obviously bend to the interests of the government and do not make necessary efforts to stop the abuses of the governing parties.

Pavel Postica, program director at the Promo-LEX Association, said that the proposed amendments are absurd; they have no logical support and it is not even clear where and why they came from. However, as a result of the monitoring carried out by Promo-LEX, with all the criticism that came from the majority of the electoral contestants, the need to monitor the elections by the civil society was never questioned. According to him, observers are those who obtain and have the legal right, according to the Electoral Code, to carry out an election monitoring activity. There are people who, based on the rights guaranteed by law, try to explain to the citizens, who do not have access to the electoral procedures, how the elections are organized. Thus, says Pavel Postica, they ensure a transparency of the process which, in essence, in some places is more closed to the general public. And directly or indirectly, it brings credibility to that process.

The president of the Center for Legal Resources of Moldova (CLRM), Vladislav Gribincea, stated that such limitations are introduced only in states with dictatorships. However, any criticism of democracy is in favor of democracy and there must be no fear of the truth. The fact that NGOs are vocal is a good thing to make governance better. The limitations proposed by the Socialist Party (SP) do not exist in countries such as the Russian Federation or Azerbaijan. For example, in Russia it is not forbidden to promote policies - if someone promotes policies on his page, he just has to say so. And in the Republic of Moldova it is proposed to absolutely ban the promotion of policies. Vladislav Gribincea mentioned that he was surprised by the fact that the Socialist Party's amendments exclude from the bill the interdiction to make electoral agitation. Thus, electoral agitation by NGOs, including foundations, would no longer be expressly prohibited. Or, the socialists were the ones who always said that the project, in the version adopted in the first reading, allows the involvement of NGOs in politics. And this is not true, because, in fact, it prohibits any form of NGO involvement in politics, and the SP amendments exclude this ban from the bill. In his opinion, it is a total dissonance with what they said before and what they are promoting now. Regarding the exclusion of the possibility of non-governmental organizations to decide on electoral programs, the president of the CLRM gave the example of environmental NGOs in relation to parties with a pronounced ecological policy. Given this ban, it is not clear what the behavior should be. The situation is similar in the case of media NGOs, if a party promotes the establishment of media censorship or the liquidation of the independent press.

On 11 June 2020, the document was adopted after the committee had examined almost 100 amendments to this draft from civil society and Parliamentary Members. [6] Thus, the draft Law

on non-commercial organizations was voted in the final reading, after almost three hours of debates in Parliament. Opposition MPs accused the parliamentary majority of analysing amendments that were not examined by the Legal Committee, thus violating the regulation. [11] Until the sitting of the Parliament, Sergiu Litvinenco also accused the chairman of the Legal Committee for Appointments and Immunities, Vasile Bolea, of falsifying the report for the Law on Non-Commercial Organizations. Litvinenco said that after the Legal Committee approved a report on the NGO Law, MP Bolea introduced 11 amendments that did not pass to the Committee. [18] It was necessary for Parliament to take a break so that the members of the Legal Committee could be convened repeatedly. Finally, 95 deputies voted "for". [7]

Some amendments to the bill have been approved, but others have been withdrawn. Thus, amendments 283, 391, 531, 1081 were withdrawn. Amendments 211, 671 were approved. Also, the deputy Vasile Bolea withdrew his amendment 241 and 282. Amendment 1041 was also withdrawn.

It should be noted that the socialist Vasile Bolea announced that he is withdrawing several amendments that previously aroused a wave of criticism from the opposition. [19] Thus, the President of the Center for Legal Resources of Moldova, Vlad Gribincea, considers that if the amendments proposed by Socialist MP Vasile Bolea were accepted by the Parliament, then this would lead to the closure of 70% of NGOs operating in the Republic of Moldova. According to him, the measures proposed by MP Bolea do not even exist in Azerbaijan or the Russian Federation, countries that are known to be the most repressive in relation to NGOs. [18]

The new law will regulate the legal framework of non-commercial organizations. Their registration and activity procedures have been simplified by linking them to international practices on free-

dom of association. The opportunity of the Law on Non-Commercial Organizations lies in the fact that, being elaborated during the years 1996-1999, the national legislation in the field of freedom of association, despite several amendments, does not offer solutions to modern realities in the respective sector. [12] The members of the Legal Committee had to examine 100 amendments to the draft law, submitted by the civil society and deputies after its adoption in the first reading, in the spring-summer 2018 session. [7]

According to the new regulations, the registration period for non-commercial organizations is reduced from 30 to 15 days, and the non-commercial organization is registered by the Public Services Agency and acquires legal personality from the moment of registration. For the registration of the non-commercial organization, of the modifications and completions to its statute, no fee is charged. The state registration body, within 15 days from the receipt of the documents, adopts the decision of registration or refusal in the registration of the non-commercial organization. At the same time, the new regulations establish the principles of establishment and cessation of non-commercial organizations, of carrying out the activity, as well as the procedure of obtaining the status of public utility. [6]

We note that the law does not overlap the current legislation, because it:

- links the special legislation on non-commercial organizations to the modernized Civil Code (in force since March 2019);

- simplifies the procedure for registering non-commercial, removes many unjustified restrictions on being a member or part of the governing bodies of non-commercial organizations (Art. 11);

- introduces a flexible system of internal organization, including the possibility for the founders to individually design their structure and administration and control bodies (Art. 17 - 20).

At the same time, this law is more restrictive compared to the legislation in force (Law on public associations, Art. 8) which does not prohibit public associations from conducting electoral agitation. The bill prohibits in absolute terms the NCOs to make electoral agitation in favor of any candidate in elections (Art. 6 paragraphs 3-5 of the bill). The draft of the law transposes into Moldovan legislation the Council of Europe **Recommendation** on the legal status of non-governmental organizations (point 13) and the recommendations of the **Venice Commission Opinion** CDL (2018)008 in the case of Romania (point 53) regarding the freedom of expression of non-commercial organizations.

According to Art. 6 the law prohibits non-commercial organizations from financially supporting political parties. Also, the provisions of the Electoral Code (Art. 41), of the Law on political parties (Art. 26 paragraph 6 letter h) and of the Fiscal Code (Art. 52 paragraph 2 letter d) which prohibit any possibility for the non-commercial organization to use its resources to financially support political parties.

In the same vein, the new law stipulates that NGOs may carry out any activity not prohibited by law, including economic activity or social entrepreneurship (Art. 6). However, it is forbidden to distribute the profit of the organization between founding members and other persons (Art. 8, paragraph 3), which excludes that, under the auspices of a non-commercial organization, an economic activity may be developed in order to obtain profit. The law also provides for the obligation of non-commercial organizations to publish the annual activity report and to present it to any applicant (Art. 7, paragraph 3).

The new law provides for the possibility of creating unions of legal entities. That is, people who want to found unions (associations) of legal entities will be able to associate as public associations, hav-

ing the same rights and possibilities until the adoption of amendments to the Modernized Civil Code. Existing legal unions will be treated by the authorities as public associations, unless the latter do not change their own form of legal organization.

If we refer to the obligation of NGOs to re-register then we note that the law does not provide for the forced reorganization of non-commercial organizations. The transitional and final provisions of the law provide that the reorganization will take place only at the request of the non-commercial organization.

Conclusions

From what is exposed in this article, we observe that the adoption of the law ended with several disputes both from the representatives of the civil society, as well as from the governing and opposition parties of the country. This was due to divergent views on various articles. However, all we have to do is follow the evolution of the application of the new law in practice, to later add a note of appreciation or criticism of the adopted law, which we hope will ultimately target the development of Moldovan society as a whole.

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